

Human Resources Development Strategy on Sustainable Tourism on Bokori Island

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Abstract

Tourism development has significant meaning when viewed from various aspects. From an economic perspective, tourism has contributed to the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) in recent years, both through foreign exchange and financial turnover. The tourism sector also opens up business opportunities for tourism services, either directly or indirectly, and opens up many job opportunities. Various countries show that the tourism industry consistently ranks 4th or 5th for foreign exchange-earners for Bungaran et al. (2017). The linkage of tourist attractions, public facilities, tourism facilities, accessibility, and the community has become an imbalance that requires a more professional handling strategy (Yoeti, 2010). Each tourism sector is located in a strategic area or region, namely an area with the primary function of tourism or potential for tourism development. It must be managed by involving more qualified Human Resources (HR), to be able to attract tourists. The object of research is the island of Bokori, Southeast Sulawesi, Indonesia. The purpose of this study is to provide a measurement of how to build the concept of a human resource development strategy on sustainable tourism on Bokori Island and to enrich some theoretical literature, mainly as a basis for identifying human resource development strategies for sustainable tourism on Bokori Island using SWOT analysis. To analyze the weaknesses, strengths, opportunities and threats faced in human resource development strategies for sustainable tourism on Bokori Island. The research uses qualitative methods. Data collection techniques were carried out through library studies and interviews with key informants. The study results show that the SO (Strength Opportunity) strategy includes Cooperation in preparing the Tridharma design of universities in developing sustainable tourism human resources. The ST (Strength Threat) strategy creates sustainable tourism human resource development and more emphasis on the quality of training than the number of participants being trained. WO (Weakness Opportunity) strategy, including curriculum development which is continuously updated. Finally, the WT (Weakness Threat) Strategy includes developing an integrated database with training and mentoring. Recommendations that can be submitted related to the policy strategy are: 1) The need to develop a sustainable tourism HR database; 2) The need to develop a sustainable tourism human resource development program; 3) Develop a roadmap for developing sustainable tourism human resources. It is hoped that after this research is carried out, further research must develop human resource development specifically for tourism managers, both from the private sector and from the Government and raise the variables of competence, work attitude and sense of belonging.

Keywords: *Strategy, Human Resource Development, Sustainable Tourism*

INTRODUCTION

Tourism development has an essential meaning when viewed from various aspects. From an economic perspective, tourism has contributed to the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) in recent years, both through foreign exchange and financial turnover. The tourism sector also opens up business opportunities for tourism services, either directly or indirectly, and opens up many job opportunities. Various countries show that the tourism industry consistently ranks 4th or 5th as a foreign exchange earner for the Bungaran country (2017). Tourism development has prospective multidimensional aspects such as regional development, economic sector development, increasing regional income from the service sector and human resource development, and growth from other supporting dimensions such as cultural, social, economic, political and legal, and government policies. This dimension revolves around world tourism development, including tourism development in Indonesia (Nyoman, 1999). The complex extent of tourism requires the Government's attention to continue to develop tourism objects subjectively. This, of course, cannot be separated from the responsibility and active role of the central Government and local governments to work together to provide facilities, facilities and infrastructure in various tourism objects, both physically and non-physically. This provision then takes root in the tourism actors themselves, consisting of the Government as the centre of policy and the community as tourism workers directly involved (Chafid, 2002).

The linkage of tourist attractions, public facilities, tourism facilities, accessibility, and the community has become an imbalance that requires a more professional handling strategy to make tourism one of the business fields. A tourism business is a business that provides goods and/or services to fulfil tourist needs and organize tourism. Each tourism sector is located in a strategic area or region, namely an area that has the primary function of tourism or has the potential for tourism development which has an important influence in several aspects, such as economic, social and cultural growth, empowerment of natural resources, environmental carrying capacity, and defence and security. Human resources manage these aspects with professional competence, including knowledge, skills, and behaviours that must be possessed, internalized, and mastered by tourism workers to develop work professionalism. (Muallisin, Isnaini, 2007).

The priority for developing the Bokori island tourism area consists of environmental, social, cultural, economic and human resources aspects that become tourism workers. However, this cannot be separated from government policies in tourism and must be implemented to realize sustainable tourism. Along with using the worker aspect in the tourism sector, tourism workers are responsible for organizing tourism in tourism objects. The competence of tourism workers, which includes knowledge, skills, and behaviour, is expected to be the basis for thinking and working well to provide services to tourists (Zuissar, 2019).

The tourism sector in Southeast Sulawesi, similar to other regions in Indonesia, is still one of the regional revenue sources. But in realizing its development, there are still various obstacles such as human resources who are vulnerable to a knowledge of tourism development, community civilization in tourist areas that are not maintained, the lack of implicit implementation of local government policies on tourism development in the field. This has resulted in several tourist areas becoming wild which are not well maintained, on the other hand, tourist areas are only needed on certain holidays such as Eid and the new year. The subjectivity of visits by local and foreign tourists to tourism objects is still quite monotonous, meaning that they only come to tourist attractions to eat, drink and bathe and then return home, and do not leave an impression on tourism owners to be developed for the better.

Many tourist areas in Southeast Sulawesi have experienced such things, one of which is the Bokori Island tourist area which is implicitly included in the territory of the Konawe Regency government but is managed by the Provincial Government and the private sector as well as the Bajo community on the coast of Soropia District. Bokori Island has the power as a tourist island with its natural beauty and coral island structure that stretches out in front of the Kendari Bay estuary. The distance to the island of Bokori varies depending on the crossing point with different transportation costs. In addition, Bokori Island does not have a river, clean water facilities, no residents, no tourist workers domiciled on the island. Most of the workers come from various coastal villages who are willing to become daily workers.

Since becoming a tourist destination in early 2000, the Government has begun to develop Bokori Island as a tourist destination by providing tourism facilities and infrastructure, including delivering tourist workers. However, there is still dual management between the district and the provincial governments. Private parties enter and rent out resting places and provide motorized boats for tourists at a relatively more expensive cost. The actions of the private sector and the community to offer motorboats and tourist attractions on the island of Bokori become a business opportunity for them to earn income. This is also a challenge for local governments to prioritize the development of facilities and infrastructure that connect coastal villages with Bokori Island. This opportunity will be illegally exploited by the private sector and the community if not realized immediately.

The phenomenon of the research results refers to the development of regional and environmental-based tourism. The priority of human resources is to prepare the knowledge and skills of workers through education and training in synergy with their work in the field then the results of the education and training will automatically change the behaviour of tourism workers where each worker will be professionally responsible for their work in the field. And will be effective, efficient and economical (Uoan Colina, 2016). This phenomenon occurs in the tourism area on the island of Bokori, which must be improved from environmental, socio-cultural, and economic aspects to enhance their knowledge, skills, and behaviour. Based on this, this research was conducted using a SWOT analysis.

According to (Thayer, 2007), SWOT analysis is a strategic planning method used to evaluate the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats that occur in a project or a business venture or assess the lines of own product lines and competitors. To perform the analysis, it is determined the purpose or identifies the object to be analyzed. Strengths and weaknesses are grouped into internal factors, while opportunities and threats are identified as external factors. So the SWOT method used in this study is a technique that uses several types of data. This method is usually developed with strategic planning used to evaluate the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats of sustainable tourism development on the island of Bokori.

The results of research (García-Melón et al., 2012) on Evaluation of Sustainable Tourism Strategy by involving stakeholders of the Government of Los Roques NP in Venezuela to determine priorities for evaluating strategic tourism procedures (Hanafi, 2009), researched determining development priorities tourism sector to determine potential tourism sector areas by referring to the Konawe Regency government document data. that tourism in Venice is not balanced with tourism policies that pay attention to the environment's carrying capacity (Russo's, 2002). Its supporting

sub-systems such as transportation and waste management are inadequate with the increasing number of tourists. Along with that, that the development of tourism on the island of Bali causes a struggle for water between the tourism industry and local communities, especially for agriculture (Cole's, 2016). Another study conducted in Kerwa, Bhopal, India, found that increasing tourism activities lead to resource exploitation and produce waste that is harmful to the environment, including the disruption of tourism activities, thereby reducing the interest of tourists to visit (Sharma, 2016).

LITERATURE REVIEW

Strategy

The strategy theory comes from the Greek word "*strategos*", which means general. Therefore, the word strategy means art and generals. This word refers to the primary concern of the organization's top management. According to Ibn Hajar (2019), strategy is a series of decisions and actions managers take to improve company performance. Strategy can also be interpreted as a potential action that requires top manager decisions and enormous company resources to achieve long-term goals. Specifically, strategy is the placement of the company's mission, setting organizational goals by binding external and internal forces, formulating specific policies and strategies to achieve goals and ensuring their proper implementation so that the organization's main goals will be conducted (Syafi'i, 2001).

Strategy denotes an overall approach related to an activity's idea, planning, and execution. In a good strategy, coordination of the work team has the theme of identifying the supporting factors under the principles of rational implementation of ideas, efficiency in funding and having tactics to achieve goals effectively (Tjiptono, 2007). Strategy is a comprehensive plan to achieve organizational goals. For companies, strategy is needed to obtain social and managerial processes. Individuals and groups get what they need and want by creating and exchanging products and value with others (Suryo, 2012). Strategy is an essential factor in achieving goals. The success of a business depends on the ability of the leader to formulate the strategy used. Strategy is very dependent on the goals, circumstances and the existing environment. Strategy is the overall effort to achieve goals and lead to developing a detailed marketing plan (Kotler, 2013).

Definition of Human Resource Development

Human Resources are productive individuals who work as drivers of an organization, be it in an institution or a company that functions as an asset (Cardoso, 2010). Its abilities must be trained and developed. Human Resources on a macro basis is the number of people of productive age in a country. Human Resources include the power of thought and physical energy possessed by each individual or human. Therefore, Human Resources become an essential element in organizational activities. What is included with Human Resources are (Gary, 2016):

1. Labor. Workers are individuals who produce goods and services in an organization. The workforce is in the age range of 15 to 64 years. The age of the product is in the age range of 20 to 40 years.
2. Experts. Experts are individuals who have unique expertise. The organization needs experts.
3. Leader. Leaders function to lead the running of the organization. Good or bad, the way the organization is in the hands of the leader.
4. Entrepreneur. Entrepreneurs are individuals who can develop their businesses. Entrepreneurs can also create jobs.
5. Manufacturer. Producers are individuals who can produce goods.
6. Consumers. Consumers are individual users of the goods produced

Human resource management is a process of managing a group of people in an organization using various techniques with the ultimate goal of developing the ability of workers to achieve the organization's vision through a series of missions and work programs set by the leadership (Ardana, 2014). With good human resource (HR) management, an organization can empower its human resources (HR) for short-term benefits and the growth, development, and self-satisfaction of human resources.

Sustainable Tourism

Sustainable development is essentially aimed at seeking an equal distribution of the product between generations, both now and in the future. Sustainable development seeks to improve people's welfare, to meet human needs and aspirations (Salim, 1990). According to the Ministry of Environment (1990), development (which is more economically oriented) can be measured its sustainability based on three criteria, namely:

1. There is no waste of use of natural resources or depletion of natural resources;
2. No pollution and other environmental impacts;
3. The activities must increase useable resources or replaceable resources.

Sustainability is not a simple concept but a complex one because many things need to be considered and interrelated in its operation. Therefore, it is crucial to improve the understanding of sustainable development, especially for policymakers at both macro and micro scales, to achieve development goals. Sustainable tourism is a tourism concept that impacts the environment, society, culture, economy for the present and the future, both for local communities and tourists. Sustainable tourism takes complete account of the current and future economic, social and environmental impacts, meeting the needs of visitors, industry, the environment, and the host community.

The need for sustainable or responsible planning and management is essential for the overall survival of the industry. As also stated in the Minister of Tourism Regulation No. 14 of 2016 concerning Guidelines for Sustainable Tourism Destinations, there are 4 (four) main pillars in tourism development. This pillar is also a criterion that has been formulated by the Global Sustainable Tourism Council, which includes:

1. Management of sustainable tourism destinations (Sustainability Management)
2. Economic utilization for local communities (Social-Economy)
3. Cultural preservation for the community and visitors (Culture)
4. Environmental preservation (Environment)

In the World Environment Protection Strategy, sustainable development is stated as a process carried out without consuming and destroying resources. Meanwhile, the most current definition of sustainable development is the development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs. (WCED, 1987). From this definition, it can be interpreted that sustainable development can be achieved by managing resources to be renewed or by switching from the use of resources that are difficult to restore to resources that are easy to continue. Therefore, this sustainable development approach can enable the use and utilization of resources, which the current generation and future generations can use.

METHODS

This research design uses a descriptive qualitative method that describes sustainable human resource development strategy on Bokori Island. This research was conducted in Konawe Regency on sustainable tourism human resource development strategies on Bokori Island. This research will be conducted for four months.

Research informants are people who can provide information about research in the form of people, objects or institutions (organizations) whose nature and circumstances are investigated (Sugiyono, 2017). That the subject is a collection of issues, variables, concepts, or phenomena (Morissan, 2012). Researchers can examine each subject to determine the nature of the population in question. There are two informants in this study, namely:

1. Key informants are the Government who knows the ins and outs of Bokori Island tourist destinations. In this case, the Head of the Southeast Sulawesi Provincial Tourism Office and the Head of the Konawe Regency Tourism Office, the Head of the Bokori Island UPTD.
2. Additional informants, namely the Soropia sub-district head, Bokori village head, Mekar Jaya village head, Bajo Indah village head, Bajoe village head, Leppe village head Tapulaga village head, community leaders, youth leaders, one person representing gender and visitors who visited at the time of data collection in this study, two people were determined with the criteria of 1 male and one female.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Human Resources development strategy in sustainable tourism is one of the strategic targets in the internal process perspective, namely increasing the quality and quantity of Human Resources in tourism. One of the sustainable tourism developments in developing human resources and tourism institutions is realizing excellent and competitive human resources. As stated in the Minister of Tourism Regulation No. 14 of 2016 concerning Guidelines for Sustainable Tourism Destinations, there are 4 (four) main pillars in tourism development. This pillar is also a criterion that has been formulated by the Global Sustainable Tourism Council, which includes:

1. Management of sustainable tourism destinations (Sustainability Management)
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SWOT Analysis in Sustainable Tourism Human Resource Development Strategy. Based on the results of literature studies and in-depth interviews conducted with apt sources, internal and external factors related to sustainable tourism human resources can be identified.

1. Strengths that can be identified consist of: First, HR development. This is the main priority of President Joko Widodo's Government and is one of the seven development agendas in the 2020-2024 RPJMN, namely: "Improving Quality and Competitive Human Resources". This priority will be a driving force/supporting capacity for the development of sustainable tourism human resources as one of the prospective sectors in Indonesia; Second, changing the focus from quantity tourism to quality tourism. This change in direction requires more qualified human resources to attract tourists to stay longer and spend their money while travelling; Third, the number of state Vocational High Schools (SMK) in the tourism sector to develop sustainable tourism human resources at the middle-high levels. Fourth, the dichotomy of public and private schools in tourism is reduced or no longer exists, especially in the five Super Priority Tourist Destinations. This will increase the strength of the sustainable tourism human resource development program.
2. Weaknesses that can be identified consist of: First, the limited number of assessors to conduct a competency test for sustainable tourism human resources. The limited number of assessors results in a limited number of competency certification examiners and becomes a weakness in developing sustainable tourism human resources. Whereas sustainable tourism human resources and having competency certificates are prerequisites to be recognized in the world of work and increase the competitiveness of human resources, including at the global level; Second, there is no integrated sustainable tourism HR database. This makes it difficult to develop sustainable tourism human resources; Third, the relatively high rate of labour mismatch is 37%-40% (data from the ILO, 2017 and the Ministry of Education and Culture, 2020). As a result, many educated workers cannot develop their abilities because their fields of work are not suitable; Fourth, sustainable tourism human resource capacity building activities emphasize training and technical guidance with a relatively large target number of participants. Intensive capacity building is required for this. Fifth, some tourist villages, which are one of the mainstays in tourism development on Bokori Island, have a weakness in the form of not having a management institution determined, making it difficult to develop sustainable tourism human resources for tourism villages managers.
3. Opportunities identified include: First, several public and private universities (PTN and PTS) have not opened tourism majors around Bokori Island. Even though this is an excellent opportunity to be utilized in the development of sustainable tourism human resources; Second, many private sectors/private companies are interested in developing human resources and Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs), including through budget allocations as part of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR); Third, the emergence of volunteers (volunteers) who want to contribute to the development of sustainable tourism human resources. These volunteers are competent individuals in their fields, such as chefs in star hotels and photographers in international media (e.g. Discovery Channel) who want to share practical expertise without the demands of a standard curriculum.
4. Threats that can be identified consist of: First, the entry of human resources from other areas that already have the required competency certification. This will threaten the human resources of the people around Bokori Island. Second, the industry has not been fully involved in developing sustainable tourism human resources. Second, the limited support of the Regional Government in developing sustainable tourism human resources. This limitation is mainly related to the budget. Most of the regional government budget, both district and provincial, is for personnel expenditure (60-70%). The rest is allocated for development and public services, including human resource development. The result of tourism, among others, requires the carrying capacity of human resources who have appropriate expertise in terms of both quality and quantity and the budget used to develop facilities and infrastructure for tourist areas.

Based on identifying internal and external factors in the form of strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats described, it is possible to analyze policy strategies that can be carried out under these factors. The method consists of:

1. SO (Strength Opportunity) Strategy, which is a strategy carried out by utilizing all strengths to obtain and take advantage of existing opportunities, namely first, Cooperation in the preparation of the Tridharma College design, mainly research and community service for both PTN and PTS under the auspices of Ministry of Tourism and Creative Economy in developing sustainable tourism human resources. This includes the design of real thematic work college programs (KKN) with a focus on developing sustainable tourism human resources, for example, in villages around tourist destinations or tourist villages. Through this collaboration, the research and community service roles of PTN and PTS can be focused on developing sustainable tourism human resources, and their implementation is monitored regularly so that their effectiveness can be identified; Second, the development of a roadmap for the development of sustainable tourism human resources. This roadmap explains the collaboration of the parties' roles and their synergies, the stages and timing of HR development in detail and operations, and the results and targets to be achieved. This roadmap can be used as an arena for coordination and synergy between stakeholders in developing sustainable tourism human resources.
2. ST (Strength Threat) Strategy, which is a strategy that is carried out by using the strengths possessed to avoid or overcome threats that come, namely: First, changes to the design of increasing tourism human resource capacity which emphasizes the quality of training rather than the number of participants trained to support the development of tourism. Quality tourism. This design change is significant to ensure that human resources participating in the

capacity building program can apply the results in the form of increasing competence practical abilities and producing the work needed, especially on Bokori Island; Second, effective collaboration between industry, academia, Government (provincial and district), community and media and collaboration between stakeholders.

3. WO (Weakness Opportunity) strategy is carried out by improving weaknesses and taking advantage of existing opportunities, namely: First, curriculum development that is continuously updated (up to date) to ensure subject matter is under tourism developments and needs. Second, the preparation of the design for the management of the Bokori Island tourist village by considering the guidelines for implementing hygiene, health, safety and environmental sustainability. Third, strengthening consistent government policies.
4. WT (Weakness Threat) strategy is a strategy carried out by trying to minimize existing weaknesses and avoid threats, namely: First, developing an integrated tourism HR database. Second, change the design of sustainable tourism human resource capacity building, emphasizing training and mentoring to realize sustainable tourism human resources. Third, establishing a program to increase human resources for sustainable tourism that is relevant to the government and village governments around Bokori Island.

CONCLUSION

From the results of the SWOT analysis conducted by identifying internal and external factors in the development of sustainable tourism human resources, the policy strategies that can be formulated are as follows:

1. SO (Strength Opportunity) strategy, namely: First, cooperation in the preparation of the Tridharma of higher education, including the Community Service Program (KKN) program in developing sustainable tourism human resources and its implementation, which is monitored regularly; and Second, the development of a detailed roadmap for the development of sustainable tourism human resources.
2. ST (Strength Threat) strategy, namely: First, changes to the design of sustainable tourism human resource capacity building which emphasizes the quality of training rather than the number of participants who are trained to support quality tourism; and Second, effective collaboration between industry, academia, Government (provincial and district), community and social media.
3. WO (Weakness Opportunity) strategy, namely: First, curriculum development which is continuously updated; Second, the preparation of a tourism village management design by considering their circumstances and position; and Third, the development of voluntary Cooperation in the development of sustainable tourism human resources.
4. WT (Weakness Threat) strategy: First, developing an integrated sustainable tourism HR database; Second, the change in the design of sustainable tourism human resource capacity building with an emphasis on training and mentoring to ensure sustainable tourism human resources can be realized. Third, establishing a program to increase human resources for sustainable tourism that is relevant to the government and village governments around Bokori Island.

The recommendations that can be submitted to be carried out by the Ministry of Tourism and Creative Economy are as follows Develop an integrated database for both tourism managers and visitors to Bokori Island. Develop a sustainable tourism human resource development program integrated between the Provincial Government and the Regency Government. Develop a roadmap for sustainable tourism human resource development to foster effective coordination and synergy between stakeholders. Develop Tourism Villages by considering guidelines for implementing cleanliness, health, safety and environmental sustainability. Develop voluntary Cooperation in the development of sustainable tourism human resources, which requires practical skills. It is hoped that after this research is carried out, further research must develop human resource development specifically for tourism managers, both from the private sector and from the Government and raise the variables of competence, work attitude and sense of belonging.

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